

New Guidelines for the Appointment, Retention and Development of Postdoctorates

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Prepared by François van Schalkwyk, as part of the “Co-creating evidence-based Higher Education & STI Policy Dialogues for a new generation of policy makers” project, coordinated by the DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence in Scientometrics and Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (SciSTIP), hosted by the Centre for Research on Evaluation, Science and Technology (CREST), Stellenbosch University, and funded by the Oppenheimer Memorial Trust (OMT).

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Contents

Preamble	4
Process followed to produce the Guidelines	8
Definitions	10
Legend	10
1. Purpose of the Guidelines	11
2. The purpose of the postdoctorate	11
3. The functions of postdoctorates	12
4. Organisational structures	13
5. Roles and responsibilities	13
6. The appointment process	15
6.1 Advertising	15
6.2 Eligibility criteria	15
6.3 Interview and selection processes	16
6.4 Appointment	16
Letter of award	16
Memorandum of Agreement, Memorandum of Understanding and Registration	17
6.5 Foreign applicants for postdoctorate positions	18
7. Tenure, renewal, termination, and other conditions	18
Extensions/Renewals	18
Early termination	18
Deportation	19
Proof of completion	19
8. Remuneration and benefits	19
8.1. Minimum and maximum amounts	19
8.2. Payment frequency	19
8.3. Tax	19
8.4. Benefits	20
Proof of income	20
9. Additional work	21
10. Research outputs and other activities	21
11. Induction and facilities	22
12. Professional development	22
13. Code of Conduct, Grievance and Disciplinary Procedures	23
Code of Conduct	23
Grievance procedures	23
Disciplinary procedures	24
Relationship between the Grievance and Disciplinary Procedures	24
Training	24
14. Policy review	24

Preamble

The postdoctoral fellow is becoming an institutionalised form of academic labour at universities around the globe, and South Africa is no exception. At the same time, the interpretation and implementation of extant rules and policies (e.g., those of the South African Receiver of Revenue, Universities South Africa, and the Department of Home Affairs) has been inconsistent across the country's higher education system. This has resulted not only in confusion about the place and purpose of the postdoctorate in the academy, but to a growing dissatisfaction among postdoctorates as they face the triple challenges of financial precarity, role confusion, and uncertain pathways into either the academy or industry.¹

Given the backdrop of an increasing number of postdoctorates in the higher education system,² the growing contribution of postdoctorates to knowledge production, the limited awareness around the existing regulations and guidelines pertaining to the hosting of postdoctorates, and the precarity of their career prospects, a number of postdoctoral administrators have been advocating for the professionalisation of the postdoctorate position at the country's universities.

To grow this nascent community of practice and to resolve the issues besetting postdoctorates at South African universities, a series of dialogues were convened by the DSI-NRF Centre of Excellence in Scientometrics and Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (SciSTIP), hosted by Stellenbosch University at its Centre for Research on Evaluation (CREST), with the support of the Oppenheimer Memorial Trust.

The following dialogues were convened, either specifically for the development of the Guidelines, or as part of a larger gathering of stakeholders:

1. The National Postdoctoral Forum, 4–5 July 2022, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch.
2. The National Postdoctorate Guidelines Workshop, 24–25 October 2022, Council on Higher Education, Pretoria.
3. The National Postdoctoral Forum, 28–29 June 2023, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch.
4. A special parallel session at the Council on Higher Education Higher Education Conference, 1–3 March 2023, CSIR, Pretoria.
5. 3rd Biannual Postdoctoral Research Conference of Africa, 18–22 September 2023, Stellenbosch University (Tygerberg Campus), Bellville.
6. Postdoctoral Hosts Dialogues, Nelson Mandela University, Gqeberha, 21 February 2024, and Oppenheimer Memorial Trust offices, Johannesburg, 23 February 2024.

The dialogues invited inputs from university administrators, government departments and agencies, funders, from postdoctorates and their societies, and from those who host postdoctorates (i.e., the academics) at South Africa's public universities.

In addition to growing the community of practice and to facilitating opportunities for the exchange of relevant information, the objective of the dialogues was to produce a set of guidelines for universities on matters pertaining to the hosting of postdoctorates and, ultimately, the professionalisation of their position within the university. It was expected that a set of guidelines would assist universities to draft or revise institutional policies so that they are in harmony with efforts to professionalise the postdoctorate at all South African universities.

¹ Van Schalkwyk, F. (2022). The 'Academic Precariat': postdoctoral fellows in South African higher education. *Briefly Speaking*, 20. CHE. <https://www.che.ac.za/file/6493/download?token=sBaJ3iMi>

² Prozesky H & Van Schalkwyk F. (2024) The profile of postdoctoral research fellows in South Africa: Trends over the past two decades. *South African Journal of Science*, (1/2), Art. #15898. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2024/15898>

The intention of the dialogues was not to produce a national policy on the postdoctorate. Rather, the objective was to produce guidelines because they would achieve the dual purposes of (1) greater standardisation across the system and compliance with existing regulations while (2) allowing for flexibility in the drafting and implementation of institutional policies that take into account the prevailing contexts at South Africa's 26 public universities.

An empirical view of the postdoctorate landscape in South Africa

Two data sources provide an empirical overview of the postdoctorate landscape in South Africa: (1) a National Survey on Postdoctoral Research Fellows conducted by SciSTIP for the National Research Foundation in 2023; and (2) the Human Sciences Research Councils' (HSRC) annual CeSTII R&D surveys. The former was commissioned by the National Research Foundation (NRF) to gain deeper insight into the number, contribution and satisfaction of postdoctorates being hosted by South African universities.

The number of postdoctorates hosted by South African universities has been increasing annually (see Figure 1),³ and at a rate which exceeds that of the growth in permanent academic staff.⁴

Figure 1. Number of postdoctorates: R&D surveys and SciSTIP Survey*, 2010–2022

* Excludes data from NWU, SMU, SPU, UKZN and UM.

Sources: Prozesky H, Van Schalkwyk F & Mouton J (2024). A National Study of Postdoctoral Research Fellows in South Africa: Report to the National Research Foundation. SciSTIP, CREST, Stellenbosch University; HSRC CeSTII R&D Surveys data in Prozesky H & Van Schalkwyk F. (2024) The profile of postdoctoral research fellows in South Africa: Trends over the past two decades. *South African Journal of Science*, (1/2), Art. #15898. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2024/15898>

Notably, the age distribution of postdoctorates shows an increasing proportion of older postdoctorates. Figure 2 shows the percentages of postdoctorates by age-bands of 10 years for the period 2016 to 2022. The data show that the proportion of older postdoctorates is increasing, most notably in the age band 41–50; the percentage of postdoctorates in this band doubled from 13% (n=188) in 2016 to 26% (n=394) in 2022.⁵ The percentage of postdoctorates in the age band 31–40 years has remained relatively stable while those in the 21 to 30-year age band has decreased from 19% (n=270) in 2016 to 7% (n=112) in 2022. The youngest reported postdoctorate was 22 (in 2016) while the oldest was 78 (in 2021).

³ Prozesky H & Van Schalkwyk F. (2024) The profile of postdoctoral research fellows in South Africa: Trends over the past two decades. *South African Journal of Science*, (1/2), Art. #15898. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2024/15898>

⁴ Prozesky H & Van Schalkwyk F. (2024) The profile of postdoctoral research fellows in South Africa: Trends over the past two decades. *South African Journal of Science*, (1/2), Art. #15898. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2024/15898>; Van Schalkwyk, F. (2022). The 'Academic Precariat': postdoctoral fellows in South African higher education. *Briefly Speaking*, 20. CHE. <https://www.che.ac.za/file/6493/download?token=sBaj3iMj>

⁵ It should be noted that age data for a relatively large number of postdoctorates was not specified in the available data: 24% in 2016; 23% in 2017; 21% in 2018 and 2019; 23% in 2020; 32% in 2021; and 37% in 2022

Figure 2. Age distribution of postdoctorates, 2016–2022

Source: Prozesky H, Van Schalkwyk F & Mouton J (2024). A National Study of Postdoctoral Research Fellows in South Africa: Report to the National Research Foundation. CREST, Stellenbosch University

In terms of nationality, 40% of postdoctorates hosted by South African universities are foreign-born. Those postdoctorates are most frequently nationals born in Nigeria, Zimbabwe, India, Cameroon and Kenya.

Table 2. Most frequent 'nationalities'* of postdocs hosted by South African public universities, 2016–2022

Nationality	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Total	%
South Africa	604	640	724	731	754	770	775	4998	60.6%
Nigeria	130	191	237	308	334	354	367	1921	23.3%
Zimbabwe	96	136	135	162	176	216	257	1178	14.3%
India	132	133	146	133	112	108	86	850	10.3%
Cameroon	38	44	49	53	50	50	46	330	4.0%
Kenya	24	39	45	53	50	52	33	296	3.6%
UK	52	49	38	44	33	28	17	261	3.2%
France	44	50	48	38	26	23	17	246	3.0%
Ghana	15	17	23	30	35	35	31	186	2.3%
Iran	16	20	28	25	31	32	19	171	2.1%
Germany	33	32	31	21	17	14	15	163	2.0%
Italy	32	33	28	21	13	12	9	148	1.8%
Ethiopia	16	22	23	24	18	17	23	143	1.7%
DRC	14	22	22	21	21	21	17	138	1.7%
Uganda	14	16	17	24	22	21	19	133	1.6%
Spain	21	24	21	20	12	11	4	113	1.4%
US	33	21	19	10	8	12	8	111	1.3%
Canada	19	15	14	17	13	11	9	98	1.2%
Lesotho	7	11	17	17	16	12	12	92	1.1%
Brazil	6	11	12	20	11	16	13	89	1.1%
Netherlands	11	11	15	17	15	9	9	87	1.1%
Malawi	9	11	11	14	10	13	17	85	1.0%
China	13	9	8	14	13	11	7	75	0.9%
Sudan	10	7	6	9	8	16	18	74	0.9%
Tanzania	7	8	11	10	8	11	11	66	0.8%
Madagascar	6	11	12	13	9	9	5	65	0.8%
Zambia	0	5	8	9	11	12	16	61	0.7%
Other	164	170	165	171	136	135	132	1073	13.0%

* Country of birth was used as a proxy for nationality.

Sources: Prozesky H, Van Schalkwyk F & Mouton J (2024). A National Study of Postdoctoral Research Fellows in South Africa: Report to the National Research Foundation. SciSTIP, CREST, Stellenbosch University

An empirical overview of the knowledge productivity of postdoctorates in South Africa

In South Africa, there are unique incentives for universities to appoint postdoctoral fellows. The primary incentive is the research output subsidy framework of the country’s Department for Higher Education and Training (DHET). The subsidy provides additional income for universities totaling approximately ZAR 3bn annually. It is in this context that South African universities are appointing an increasing number of postdoctoral fellows (see Table 3) often with the requirement that they produce a minimum of two publications per annum.

Table 3. Number of publications per postdoctorate per university, 2020–2022

	2020			2021			2022		
	<i>Pubs</i>	<i>Postdocs</i>	<i>Pubs/postdoc</i>	<i>Pubs</i>	<i>Postdocs</i>	<i>Pubs/postdoc</i>	<i>Pubs</i>	<i>Postdocs</i>	<i>Pubs/postdoc</i>
CPUT	77	64	1,20	122	76	1,61	130	81	1,60
CUT	35	17	2,06	43	13	3,31	39	16	2,44
DUT	102	17	6,00	162	29	5,59	170	31	5,48
MUT	22	13	1,69	29	15	1,93	72	18	4,00
NMU	136	65	2,09	118	109	1,08	134	140	0,96
RU	215	104	2,07	209	101	2,07	149	112	1,33
SU	606	347	1,75	653	336	1,94	641	295	2,17
TUT	112	59	1,90	91	51	1,78	109	49	2,22
UCT	619	348	1,78	610	334	1,83	613	297	2,06
UFH	133	8	16,6	76	27	2,81	53	30	1,77
UFS	402	111	3,62	441	182	2,42	496	146	3,40
UJ	623	414	1,50	715	444	1,61	872	457	1,91
UL	28	5	5,60	51	11	4,64	35	20	1,75
UNISA	136	41	3,32	151	44	3,43	223	127	1,76
UNIVEN	39	17	2,29	32	15	2,13	36	11	3,27
UNIZULU	84	28	3,00	61	19	3,21	47	26	1,81
UP	486	300	1,62	575	299	1,92	478	303	1,58
UWC	198	53	3,74	145	36	4,03	128	129	0,99
VUT	44	18	2,44	45	14	3,21	25	17	1,47
WITS	434	222	1,95	502	241	2,08	487	150	3,25
WSU	6	5	1,20	28	12	2,33	109	28	3,89

* Excludes data from NWU, SMU, SPU, UKZN and UM

Source: Prozesky H, Van Schalkwyk F & Mouton J (2024). A National Study of Postdoctoral Research Fellows in South Africa: Report to the National Research Foundation. SciSTIP, CREST, Stellenbosch University

An empirical overview of issues facing postdoctorates in South Africa

According to the OECD (2022),

Doctorate level attainment in the populations of OECD countries is rising fast. Many doctorate holders find themselves in a long period of postdoctoral work on temporary, and often short-term or undesired part-time contracts in academia. The precarity experienced by early-career researchers is having detrimental effects on their well-being, as high levels of competition have created unkind and aggressive working conditions.

A recent national large-scale survey of postdoctorates at South African universities⁶ concluded that:

1. The primary reason for taking a postdoctorate position is to enhance future employment prospects.
2. Many postdoctorates hope to pursue an academic career, but face challenges in securing permanent academic positions and with regard to personal career progression. One in every

⁶ Prozesky H, Van Schalkwyk F & Mouton J (2024). A National Study of Postdoctoral Research Fellows in South Africa: Report to the National Research Foundation. SciSTIP, CREST, Stellenbosch University

- four postdoctorates surveyed had held multiple consecutive postdoctorate positions.
3. The job market for postdoctorates in South Africa is perceived as poor, especially by non-South Africans.
 4. Postdoctorates plan to leave South Africa primarily to seek better job opportunities, but also due to immigration rules or visa issues, which constitute major challenges for postdoctorates.
 5. Postdoctorates are highly satisfied with the opportunities they are given to work on interesting projects and to interact with high-quality researchers. Factors contributing to a successful postdoctorate experience include quality research, supportive colleagues, mentoring, and communication.
 6. Postdoctorates express dissatisfaction with what they perceive as low levels of income, and a lack of support for training and career development, as well as discrimination and bias. Postdoctorates in South Africa face issues related to remuneration, employment benefits, access to financial products, work roles and requirements, and contractual issues.
 7. Postdoctorates desire to contribute to teaching and supervision, but often lack the opportunity.
 8. Discrimination and harassment are observed and/or experienced by some postdoctorates.

At the same time, to benefit from the tax exemption granted to postdoctorates on condition that they are appointed as bursary recipients, universities are not employing postdoctorates as permanent (or contract) academic staff, nor are they registering postdoctorates as students. There is a general lack of awareness around the existing directives, policies and guidelines pertaining to the postdoctorate position. And as is the case in OECD countries, postdoctorates face a precarious future in relation to their academic career prospects (CHE 2022).

It is against this background that university administrators responsible for postdoctorates programmes initiated a process to professionalise the postdoctorate at South Africa's universities.

Process followed to produce the Guidelines

The process to produce the "New Guidelines for the Appointment, Retention and Development of Postdoctorates" is illustrated in the graphic below. It shows the process of identifying and convening a self-organised group of postgraduate administrators from an emerging community of practice around a specific policy issue, in this case, the professionalisation of the postdoctoral position in the university. In the early phases of the process, this group formed the core for consultative fora which then resulted in the drafting of a set of guidelines for universities to follow should they require guidance on how to professionalise the postdoctoral position at their respective universities.

The process of producing the draft guidelines through consultation is informed by the available data on postdoctorates at South African universities; in this case, primarily data from three sources: (1) the SciSTIP tracer study on doctoral graduates in South Africa; (2) the HSRC CeSTII R&D surveys; and (3) the NRF-SciSTIP National Survey of Postdoctorates in South Africa.

The process continued with a series of dialogues in which the draft guidelines were discussed and revised in an iterative process. The dialogues included a broader set of stakeholders, including postdoctorates, funders, government departments, academic staff who host postdoctorates, organisations in the higher education system (e.g., USAf and CHE), and administrators from research offices and other relevant structures at universities.

The dialogues process included the dissemination of the proceedings and of the drafts of the guidelines following each dialogue, as well publications to raise awareness of the process and the progress towards producing a useful set of guidelines.

The outcomes of the dialogues have been two-fold: (1) a final version of the national guidelines for professionalising the postdoctorate; and (2) improved practice at universities across the country in the management and hosting of postdoctorates. Part of the final stages of the process also ensured buy-in, i.e., an acceptance of the guidelines by a broad range of stakeholders. The diagram below presents the steps in the process and specifically the final endorsement of the guidelines by key stakeholders.

Both outcomes are expected to create a positive feedback loop which strengthens the community of practice related to the management, hosting and professionalisation of postdoctorates at South Africa’s universities, and which will institutionalise the guidelines.

Definitions

- “department” means the academic department, division, centre, or institute at a university where a postdoctorate is registered
- “DVC” means deputy vice-chancellor
- “fellowship” means the grant or stipend awarded to the postdoctorate for their personal expenses for the duration of the postdoctoral research period
- “host” means an academic staff member in a relevant academic department, centre, research entity or institute at a university who acts as supervisor and mentor to a postdoctorate
- “MoA” means memorandum of agreement
- “MoU” means memorandum of understanding
- “postdoc” means a postdoctoral fellow
- “postdoc office” means the person(s) and/or organisational entity at a public university responsible for the management of postdoctoral affairs
- “SARS Binding Class Ruling: Higher Education South Africa” is a tax ruling issued in accordance with section 78(2) of the Tax Administration Act, No. 28 of 2011. The ruling applies to Universities South Africa (USAf)
- “university” means all public universities in South Africa
- “USAf” refers to Universities South Africa, formerly Higher Education South Africa (HESA)
- “USAf policy” refers to the undated Annexure 2: “Policy for Post Doctoral Research Fellowships / Post Doctoral Research Fellows” referred to in the SARS Binding Class Ruling.

Legend

- [!]** Guideline deviates from SARS Binding Class Ruling and USAf Policy
- SARS** Guideline is informed by and complies with the SARS Binding Class Ruling
- USAf** Guideline is informed by and complies with the USAf Policy of 2013
- DHA** Guideline is informed by the Department of Home Affairs

1. Purpose of the Guidelines

Providing clear and unambiguous guidelines on the appointment, retention and development of postdocs will assist universities in drafting or revising institutional policies so that they are in harmony with efforts to professionalise the postdoctorate at South African universities. This process should strike a balance between national and institutional priorities, and the well-being of postdoctorates.

This document is an attempt to provide the guidelines required. It is the outcome of research and surveys conducted on the status of the postdoctoral fellows in South Africa,⁷ as well as several dialogues with key stakeholders who attended several workshops/for a referred to in the Preamble of this document.

This document should be read in parallel with the SARS Binding Class Ruling: Higher Education South Africa, issued in accordance with section 78(2) of the Tax Administration Act, No. 28 of 2011. The ruling applies to Universities South Africa (USAf) and the universities it represents (the class members). The ruling states that USAf has “adopted a best practice policy pertaining to PDRFs [postdoctoral research fellows]. The PDRF Policy contains the rules and procedures to be followed by the Class Members in respect of the funding and advertising of PDRFs, the requirements and application process for PDRFs, and the process to be followed in awarding, accepting, payment and extension of a PDRF. The Class Members have indicated that they will grant PDRFs based on the PDRF policy at all times”.

2. The purpose of the postdoctorate

The purpose of the postdoctorate position within universities is to provide opportunities for the training and development of new doctoral graduates in support of their careers. Skills and knowledge gained may provide the foundation for a successful career in the academy by familiarizing postdoctorates with the expectations, systems, cultures, and values of universities. The development of postdoctorates may equally prepare them for alternative career pathways (e.g., professional positions within universities, or research management positions in the public sector or in industry) in which they may draw on skills such as project management, problem solving, budgeting and negotiation attained during their tenure as postdoctorates.

⁷ Van Schalkwyk F (2022). The ‘academic precariat’: Postdoctoral fellows in South African higher education. *Briefly Speaking*. 20:1–14. Council on Higher Education. <http://www.che.ac.za/file/6493/download?token=sBaJ3iMj>; Prozesky H, Van Schalkwyk F & Mouton J (2024). A National Study of Postdoctoral Research Fellows in South Africa: Report to the National Research Foundation. SciSCTIP, CREST, Stellenbosch University; Prozesky H & Van Schalkwyk F. (2024) The profile of postdoctoral research fellows in South Africa: Trends over the past two decades. *South African Journal of Science*, (1/2), Art. #15898. <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2024/15898>

According to the USAf policy of 2013 [USAf], the purposes of the postdoctorate position are to:

1. place higher education institutions at the forefront of research and innovation;
2. generate new knowledge and transfer knowledge and skills;
3. enable outstanding doctoral graduates to obtain experience of research and innovation at higher education institutions;
4. provide an opportunity to promising young researchers from different universities to enhance their research skills and expertise;
5. expand on existing research and ideas and to pursue new lines of research;
6. interact with other academics and postdoctoral fellows;
7. emphasise an increase in publication outputs;
8. establish and enhance South African intellect;
9. develop knowledge for stakeholders such as the government, business, industry, and social communities; and
10. promote national and international conference attendance by postdoctoral fellows and the presentation of research papers at these conferences.

3. The functions of postdoctorates

Given the purpose of the postdoctorate position, they should, in addition to their function as researchers, be expected to fulfil a broad range of functions within the university. These may include but are not limited to: conceptualising and designing new research projects; managing research projects; securing funding for research; reviewing publications and funding proposals; undertaking the supervision and/or mentoring of postgraduate students; teaching undergraduate and postgraduate students; fulfilling academic duties (such as serving on committees); and initiating or supporting the host institution's community engagement activities. Given the multiple functions that postdoctorates may fulfil, the following guidelines are proposed:

- The institutional policies related to postdoctorates at South African universities should clearly set out all the functions that postdoctorates are expected to fulfil.
- Each host and their postdocdorate should draft an individual development plan to set out clearly:
 - the expectations of the host in terms of the functions of the postdoctorate during their tenure, and
 - the support to be provided by the host (including, but not limited to, office space, computers and laptops, lab space and equipment, regular meetings and feedback) in order for the postdoctorate to meet the agreed-upon expectations.
- Include in the individual development plan details on how and when the plan will be reviewed.
- The individual development plan should align with any expectations of the funder(s), including those of the host institution in the case of internally funded postdoctorates.
- A copy of the completed individual development plan should be filed with the relevant organisational unit responsible for postdoctorates.
- If at this stage the host and the postdoctorate cannot agree on the functions of the postdoctorate, both parties should consult the university's postdoctorate office.

4. Organisational structures

- 4.1. The university should establish a single entity responsible for managing and coordinating postdoctorate affairs.
- 4.2. The university should consider the establishment of a postdoctorate committee with representatives from university management and administration, academic faculties, and postdoctorates at the same university.
- 4.3. Postdoctorates should either establish a representative body and/or elect representatives with whom the university can engage on matters pertaining to postdoctorates.

5. Roles and responsibilities

The postdoctorate policies of universities should set out the roles and responsibilities of the postdoctorate, the academic host, the postdoctorate office, and the university.

5.1 Role and responsibilities of the postdoctorate

Although expectations from postdoctorates, as agreed upon in individual MoUs, will vary depending on the environments in which they are hosted, there are a number of general expectations that a university may have of its postdoctorates. These include the following:

- 5.1.1 Accurate and meticulous record keeping of all activities (e.g., research, teaching, supervision, service, grant-writing, etc.) and the regular provision of research data to the relevant host.
- 5.1.2 Undertaking output-driven research. Articles in journals, books, book chapters or conference proceedings accredited by the Department of Higher Education and Training should be achievable within the duration of the fellowship, as agreed upon in the MoU.
- 5.1.3 Contribution to the research ethos of the host environment. This contribution should come in the form of willing participation in meetings, research seminars (especially those involving postgraduate students), knowledge transfer to colleagues and students; and spending significant proportion of their time on the university campus(es).
- 5.1.4 Contribution to the operation of a research laboratory where appropriate and as agreed with the relevant academic host.
- 5.1.5 Contribution towards the university's goals, vision, and mission.
- 5.1.6 Submission of progress reports to funders, where and when required.
- 5.1.7 The completion of an exit form before leaving the university.

5.2 Role and responsibilities of the academic host

Academic hosts of postdoctorates accept responsibility for the following:

- 5.2.1 Providing the postdoctorate with the research equipment and space required by the postdoctorate to complete their research and as should be agreed upon in the relevant MoU.
- 5.2.2 Keeping an up-to-date record of the research done by the postdoctorate.
- 5.2.3 Meeting with the postdoctorate on a regular basis and providing guidance and support for the research to be undertaken by the postdoctorate.
- 5.2.4 Ensuring that the postdoctorate is familiar with the university's postdoctorate policy.
- 5.2.5 Ensuring that the postdoctorate is informed of or is familiar with, and has access to, all institutional policies related to research.
- 5.2.6 Ensuring that the postdoctorate is informed of or is familiar with, and has access to, institutional

- policies related to the university's Code of Conduct.
- 5.2.7 Ensuring that sufficient research funding is available for the postdoctorate to complete the research project(s) as set out in the MoU.
 - 5.2.8 Communicating in writing the required working hours to the postdoctorate before the uptake of the fellowship.
 - 5.2.9 Submitting copies of the relevant documents, including the application with the necessary supporting documents, the necessary approvals, advertisement for the postdoctorate position, the Letter of Award, MoU, and MoA, or any other documents that might be required in terms of institutional processes, to the postdoctorate office.
 - 5.2.10 Informing the postdoctorate office and the postdoctorate in writing of the premature termination of a fellowship.
 - 5.2.11 Informing the postdoctorate office in writing when fellowships are extended after the completion of an award and adhering to the required administrative process for the extension period.
 - 5.2.12 Ensuring that the proposed research project is structured in such a way that the desired outputs are achievable within the duration of the fellowship.
 - 5.2.13 Providing mentorship and professional training opportunities to the postdoctorate.

5.3 Departmental and faculty roles

- 5.3.1 Providing orientation to the department, centre, or institute in which the postdoctorate will undertake their research.
- 5.3.2 Providing access to department, centre, or institute facilities.
- 5.3.3 Managing, and attempting to resolve, any grievances, complaints, or disciplinary matters that either the academic host or the postdoctorate may report.

5.4 Roles and responsibilities of the postdoctorate office

- 5.4.1 The postdoctorate office should receive and administer postdoctoral fellowships.
- 5.4.2 Timely payment of the agreed upon stipend on the stipulated dates.
- 5.4.3 Assist postdoctorates to find suitable accommodation or refer postdoctorates to other university structures that are in a position to do so.
- 5.4.4 Provide the necessary guidance and support in terms of visa renewal or application.
- 5.4.5 Participate in the process of approving new postdoctorate applications and renewal forms.
- 5.4.6 Advise postdoctorate hosts on developments and changes in relation to postdoctorate regulations, policies and procedures.
- 5.4.7 Advise postdoctorate representatives and postdoctorate representative bodies on developments and changes in relation to postdoctorate regulations, policies and procedures.

5.5 Roles and responsibilities of the university

- 5.5.1 The university should have in place a postdoctorate office responsible for receiving, administering, and managing postdoctoral fellowships.
- 5.5.2 The university should recognise the right of postdoctorates to formally organise themselves into representative bodies as well as to elect their representatives on university structures.
- 5.5.3 The university should ensure that an enabling institutional environment is provided to postdoctorates. This includes providing the postdoctorate with a conducive and safe working environment in order to meet the deliverables as agreed upon in the relevant MoU.

6. The appointment process

6.1 Advertising

All postdoctorate positions must be advertised to comply with the SARS regulations governing 'open bursaries'. [SARS]

The purpose of advertising new or vacant postdoctorate positions is to attract applications from postdoctoral candidates from other universities. The advertisement must therefore be placed in at least one public forum [USAf].

The university's intranet or internal electronic bulletin board does not qualify as a public forum. Examples of acceptable public forums include the NRF's website, newspapers, social media, specialist higher education news websites (e.g., University World News), and academic and professional social networking platforms (e.g., ResearchGate, LinkedIn).

Universities are advised to:

- 6.1.1 Develop a template for the advertising of new postdoctorate positions.
- 6.1.2 Include as much information as necessary in the template to ensure a fair application process (e.g., eligibility criteria; term and any renewal conditions; the value of bursary and whether visa, relocation and travel costs are included; allowances for breaks in an academic career; expected tasks and outputs).
- 6.1.3 Make the template available in electronic format for all departments, faculties, research entities and schools.
- 6.1.4 Ensure that all postdoctorate advertisements are checked by the postdoctorate office to ensure compliance with SARS and other regulations
- 6.1.5 Ensure that a copy of the final version of the postdoctorate advertisement is filed with the postdoctorate office.
- 6.1.6 Place advertisements for new postdoctorate positions for a period of no less than 4 weeks.

6.2 Eligibility criteria

6.2.1 The proposed candidate

- must hold, or will soon hold, an appropriate doctoral degree, [USAf]
- must not be or plan to be the recipient of more than one postdoctorate bursary at any given time,
- must be able to provide proof of having graduated with a doctoral degree or that the awarding of the degree is imminent,
- may be of any age, gender, or nationality (subject only to the visa regulations of the Department of Home Affairs).

6.2.2 It is recommended that the following eligibility criteria only be applied in cases where more established researchers are required to fill a postdoctorate position:

- have a research track record and/or publication record, [USAf]
- have experience of delivering papers at conferences. [USAf]

6.2.3 At the time of the *awarding of the postdoctorate position*, the candidate should have

- graduated with their doctorate degree, [USAf]
- graduated with their doctoral degree within the previous five years. [USAf]

The five-year limit is imposed to prevent repeated renewal of postdoctorate fellowships and the undesirable consequence of 'serial postdoctorates' without prospects for furthering their careers either within or outside of the academy.

Although not provided for in the [USAf] policy, universities should give consideration to those candidates whose academic careers were interrupted during the five-year period following their doctoral graduation, particularly in cases where the disruption was for reasons beyond their control (e.g., illness, unplanned pregnancy, compulsory public service, etc.).

- 6.2.4 An award is regarded as being equivalent to the duration of the funding available for the postdoctorate bursary. A postdoctoral fellowship may be extended beyond the time frame specified in an Award Letter provided that sufficient funding is available. The extension, however, should then be regarded as a new award, and as such can only be awarded if the postdoctorate was awarded their doctoral degree no more than five years prior to the date of the award.

6.3 Interview and selection processes

- 6.3.1 The academic host, in consultation with the head of department, is responsible for:

- accepting and acknowledging the applications of postdoctorates;
- selecting an appropriate candidate.

- 6.3.2 Interviewing candidates should be done by a constituted panel consisting of various stakeholders, including:

- the host;
- academic staff from within the host department;
- a member of the management and/or administration within the university;
- a member (or a delegate) of the international office (in the case of foreign postdoctorates); and
- a member (or a delegate) of the postdoctorate office.

- 6.3.3 Candidates may be former students, or current or former staff members, but preference should be given to candidates who hold doctoral degrees from universities other than the university from which they obtained their doctoral degree.

- 6.3.4 The candidate's intended research project or programme must fall within the university's or the host's research objectives.

- 6.3.5 Sufficient infrastructure and basic funding must be available for the postdoctorate applicant's intended research.

- 6.3.6 A suitable mentor (either an academic staff member or a research fellow, preferably but not necessarily, a specialist in the candidate's research field) must be available to guide the postdoctoral candidate's proposed research activities.

6.4 Appointment

Letter of award

- 6.4.1 After the interviewing and selection process is completed, the host academic must supply the postdoctorate office with the following details of the chosen applicant [USAf]:

- the name and full contact details of the selected candidate;
- the amount of the award and its source/s (description of the original source/s and the University cost entity/centre from where it will be paid);
- the term of the award;
- proof of doctoral qualification (copy of doctoral degree or proof of satisfactory fulfilment of the university's requirements for a PhD);
- curriculum vitae ("CV"), clearly indicating the applicant's research publications;
- a copy of the applicant's identity document or passport photo page; and

- in the case of an international fellow, a copy of the applicant's Visa.
- 6.4.2 All postdoctorates are to be provided with a Letter of Award on the university's letterhead, outlining the details and terms of their appointment at the university. The Letter of Award should be drafted by the postdoctoral office, and signed by both the academic host and the postdoctoral scholar [USAf].
- 6.4.3 The Letter of Award will provide the following information:
- research expectations;
 - the period of the appointment;
 - the annual stipend;
 - frequency of payment;
 - any benefits offered by the university;
 - any additional funding provided (e.g., for relocation, conference attendance, research-related expenses);
 - personal leave days;
 - indication that renewal of the postdoctorate is subject to available funding and satisfactory performance;
 - the requirement for repayment in the case of non-completion of the postdoctorate fellowship;
 - any applicable terms or conditions, as long as they do not contravene the SARS Binding Class Ruling;
 - a deadline of no less than 4 (four) weeks to accept the award;
 - processes and contact persons should the candidate wish to query or negotiate the terms of the award; and
 - details of the postdoctorate's host.
- 6.4.4 A copy of the Letter of Award must be placed on file at the postdoctorate office. [USAf]

Memorandum of Agreement, Memorandum of Understanding and Registration

- 6.4.5 By way of acceptance, a postdoctorate must complete and sign a Memorandum of Agreement (or any contract/legally binding document) with the university for registration as a postdoctorate.
- 6.4.6 Together with the host, the postdoctorate must also complete a Memorandum of Understanding, which outlines the general conditions of the award and the research to be undertaken. The Memorandum of Understanding should be legally binding and must include:
- the frequency, purpose, and content of meetings between the academic host and postdoctorate;
 - expected workdays and hours (including when the postdoctorate is expected to be on-campus);
 - expected outputs; and
 - processes for dealing with complaints and grievances.
- 6.4.7 The university's postdoctorate policy must be appended to the Memorandum of Understanding. Acceptance of the Memorandum of Understanding must imply acceptance of the university's policies pertaining to postdoctorates.
- 6.4.8 Upon completion, both the Memorandum of Understanding and the Memorandum of Agreement must be sent to the postdoctorate office.
- 6.4.9 Copies of these completed documents should be retained on file by the postdoctorate office and the academic host.
- 6.4.10 Completion of the above-mentioned documentation must be followed by a registration process at the university.

6.5 Foreign applicants for postdoctorate positions

- 6.5.1 Prospective postdoctorates who are not citizens of South Africa should apply to the Department of Home Affairs for the special postdoctorate visitor's visa (Section 11[1][b] Visitors Visa) which can be issued by the Department of Home Affairs for a period of up to three years. [DHA]
- 6.5.2 Foreign postdoctorates are not permitted to work on a visitor's visa. This *includes* the 12 hours of work per month permitted by the SARS Binding Class ruling. [SARS]
- 6.5.3 Universities are encouraged to top up the stipends of foreign postdoctorates by 12 hours multiplied by the prescribed university rate for researchers with a PhDs. (For example, 12 hours x R350 per hour equals an additional stipend of R4,200 per month.) This additional stipend should be introduced to replace the opportunity for international postdoctorates to earn additional income as prohibited by visa conditions of the Visitor's Visa issued by the Department of Home Affairs.

7. Tenure, renewal, termination, and other conditions

- 7.1 Postdoctorates should be appointed for a minimum period of 2 (two) years [USAf], subject to renewal of their Award which, in turn, should be based on clearly defined and measurable performance criteria.
- 7.2 Postdoctorates may not be appointed for longer than 5 (five) years on a single Award.
- 7.3 A postdoctorate may not register for any degree at their host university or at another higher education institution during the term of the postdoctoral fellowship, without written permission from the host and any other relevant authorities at the host university.

Extensions/Renewals

- 7.4 Renewal of postdoctorate bursary awards are permitted subject to:
 - 7.4.1 satisfactory performance of the postdoctorate as per the terms of the postdoctorate's MoU;
 - 7.4.2 compliance with the university's code of conduct;
 - 7.4.3 the postdoctorate being within 5 (years) of completing their doctoral degree at the time at which the renewed award will be taken up. Exceptions to this guideline may be considered but not encouraged, particularly if a postdoctorate's academic career has been interrupted for reasons beyond their control.

Early termination

- 7.5 Should a postdoctorate wish to terminate his/her fellowship prior to the date agreed upon in the MoU, he/she should give at least 30 (thirty) days' written notice to their host.
- 7.6 Should the host wish to terminate the hosting of a postdoctorate, he/she needs to inform the postdoctorate office and the postdoctorate in writing at least 30 (thirty) days in advance. If required, the host and postdoctorate should have recourse to the postdoctoral dispute resolution processes of the university.
- 7.7 The basis of any termination must be as per the conditions set out in the MoU between the academic host and postdoctorate. This is critical because postdoctorates are not employees of the university and therefore the provisions and protections of South Africa's labour laws are not applicable to postdoctorates.
- 7.8 The first level for dealing with termination or other issues is either the faculty or school, whereafter, if the termination is challenged, it may be escalated to the university's postdoctorate office and legal division.
- 7.9 A postdoctorate and his/her host are required to inform the postdoctorate office and submit an "exit

form”, when the postdoctorate terminates his/her tenure at the university.

Deportation

- 7.10 To account for instances where a foreign postdoctorate’s award is terminated prior to its completion, the university’s policy must be clear on who issues the required documentation regarding the deportation of the postdoctorate and who will carry the cost of the deportation, in line with the country’s immigration laws.

Proof of completion

- 7.11 Hosts, with the support of the postdoctorate office, should provide postdoctorates with either a certificate of completion or with a letter of recommendation on completion of their tenure as a postdoctorate.

8. Remuneration and benefits

8.1. Minimum and maximum amounts

- 8.1.1 There is no maximum amount that can be awarded as a postdoctorate bursary. The maximum amount of funding for a postdoctoral fellowship is not prescribed by any law [SARS], and should be at the discretion of the relevant host in consultation with the postdoctorate office.
- 8.1.2 There is no minimum amount that can be awarded as a postdoctorate bursary. As of 2022, universities are determining their own minimum bursary amounts of R200,000-R250,000 per annum. No maximum amounts are set, but universities provide a guideline for the maximum of bursaries awarded of R350,000-R400,000 per annum, with some universities requiring motivation letters for bursaries that exceed these amounts. In 2024, the NRF adjusted its funding for postdoctorates to R350,000 per annum.
- 8.1.3 The remuneration of postdoctorates should not be fixed and should be in line with the real costs of living in different parts of the country. It is, however, recommended that universities agree, via a suitable structure, on a minimum amount for any postdoctorate bursary awarded in South Africa. This structure should be in a position to hold universities accountable and should ensure the annual revision of the minimum amount.
- 8.1.4 Payment requests to increase the initial postdoctorate bursary award amount (which is reflected in the Letter of Award) must be permitted by the specific bursary award conditions and must be accompanied by a formal letter from the academic host specifying the amendment of the bursary amount. [USAf]

8.2. Payment frequency

[USAf] prescribes that payments should be made

- quarterly if the bursary is funded from university funds,
- bi-annually if the bursary is funded from external funds, and that single, annual payments are not permitted.

This document recommends that payments should be made monthly and that payments should be on a fixed day of each month. [!]

8.3. Tax

- 8.3.2 The income derived from the payment of postdoctorate bursaries is exempt from taxation. [SARS]

8.3.3 Additional income derived from performing additional work permitted (see Section 8), is taxable according to the rules and taxation tables of SARS. [USAf]

8.4. Benefits

- 8.4.1 Postdoctorates are not employees of the university, and they can therefore not qualify for any employee benefits, including, but not limited to, medical aid, retirement benefits or accommodation allowances. [USAf]
- 8.4.2 Bursary amounts should be calculated on the basis that postdoctorates will incur the costs of their own medical insurance and membership of retirement schemes.
- 8.4.3 Bursaries should include accommodation allowances.
- 8.4.4 Bursaries should make provision for the following travel costs likely to be incurred by postdoctorates, subject to available funds:
- relocation (e.g., the cost of one return flight; airport transfer; visa; temporary accommodation on arrival)
 - research (e.g., for fieldwork)
- 8.4.5 Any accommodation and travel costs to be covered by the host/university should be indicated in the Letter of Award.
- 8.4.6 According to the regulations of the Department of Home Affairs, international postdoctorates are required to become members of a South African medical aid. Should a postdoctorate have been at the university for a period of more than 30 (thirty) days without medical aid cover, he/she will be in contravention of this regulation and the appointment of such a postdoctorate can be cancelled due to non-compliance. It is the postdoctorate's responsibility to submit proof of membership of a South African medical aid to the postdoctorate office. [DHA]
- 8.4.7 Universities should note the additional conditions that external funders may insist upon in supporting a postdoctorate bursary award, and that these conditions may contradict institutional rules, an unwillingness to provide funding if a postdoctorate does not receive benefits and/or if the university deducts any amounts (e.g., indirect or overhead costs) from the funding.
- 8.4.8 Postdoctorates shall, at the discretion of the academic host's department, be eligible to participate in any of the university's research incentive schemes to the extent that any financial incentives are paid into an account used only for expenses related to the postdoctorates' research activities. The terms and conditions of the postdoctorate's participation in any incentive scheme must be set out in the MoU between the academic host and the postdoctorate.

Proof of income

Postdoctorates face many challenges related to their inability to provide from their host university a pay slip as proof of income. These challenges include obtaining finance (to purchase a car or a property), signing rental agreements, taking out cell phone contracts, etc.

- 8.4.9 Universities should provide postdoctorates with a letter confirming the duration of the fellowship, the value of the fellowship, and the amounts and frequency of payments made to the postdoctorate.
- 8.4.10 The time required to issue a letter and the organizational unit or person(s) responsible for producing it, should be indicated in the postdoctorate policy.

9. Additional work

- 9.1 The express purpose of a postdoctorate is to engage in a period of uninterrupted research [USAf] as well as other relevant tasks as stipulated in the university's policies and/or the MoU between a postdoctorate and their host. As bursary recipients, postdoctorates may not do any additional work related to their research in return for payment, for example, contract research. [USAf] However, certain bursary schemes may make provision for postdoctorates to do additional unrelated work. [USAf]
- 9.2 Where extra work is permitted in terms of the bursary scheme, up to 12 hours weekly of additional paid work may be undertaken. This is to be paid at the university rate for casual work for workers with a PhD and must not be paid by means of the postdoctorate bursary system but via the university's salary system. These payments are taxable in accordance with the prevailing tax legislation. [USAf]
- 9.3 This guideline recommends that the matter of additional work should be included in the agreement (MoU) between the academic host and the postdoctorate, and may vary depending on, inter alia, the expectations of the academic host and the experience of the postdoctorate.
- 9.4 Regardless of the university's position on additional work, the postdoctorate policy must state clearly whether additional work is permitted as well as the permissible conditions under which additional work may be taken on by postdoctorates.
- 9.5 Foreign postdoctorates on a Visitor's Visa for Postdoctoral Fellows are, in terms of the visa, not permitted to do any additional work.

10. Research outputs and other activities

A postdoctorate is generally expected to conduct research and to publish from that research during their tenure as a postdoctorate. They may also be expected to assist with or supervise research-related activities and/or undertake teaching responsibilities. These may include number, type, and frequency of publications to be produced; number and value of grants to be secured; number of masters' students to supervise and/or co-supervise; number of doctoral students to supervise or co-supervise; number of hours of teaching; number of students to mentor; academic duties to be undertaken; number of community engagement or service hours.

- 10.1 Should the university have specific requirements of all its postdoctorates in terms of expected outputs and activities, then these should be stated clearly in the postdoctorate policy. This guideline does not encourage the setting of blanket expectations and outputs for postdoctorates because of differences across disciplines and between postdoctorates (in terms of experience) that have a direct bearing on the ability of postdoctorates to produce a set number of outputs in a fixed period.
- 10.2 As recommended by these guidelines, should the university not have specific, measurable requirements of its postdoctorates, then any expected outputs and activities should be indicated in the MoU between the academic host and the postdoctorate.
- 10.3 The MoU should make explicit the attribution of authorship and/or supervision as they relate to the outputs to be produced by the postdoctorate.

- 10.4 Expected outputs should be realistic to account for, for example, potential delays in obtaining ethics clearance, availability of materials and equipment, time from submission to publication, etc.
- 10.5 Expected outputs should place emphasis on the quality of the outputs to be produced, rather than on the quantity of outputs to be produced.

11. Induction and facilities

- 11.1 The postdoctorate office and/or the host should offer orientation for all new postdoctorates.
- 11.2 It is recommended that all postdoctorates attend an orientation within their first 3 (three) months on campus. Orientations should cover topics including:
 - understanding the appointment;
 - information packs on the university and the geography of its precincts;
 - guidance to accessing the amenities and facilities available;
 - guidance to accessing university services including advice and support structures offered by the university;
 - building a successful relationship between the host and postdoctorate;
 - professional development opportunities;
 - wellness and occupational health;
 - introduction to the postdoctoral representative body (if applicable);
 - funding and fellowship support and opportunities; and
 - meeting postdoctorates from other departments and faculties.
- 11.3 Postdoctorates should be afforded the opportunity to ask the postdoctorate office any questions they may have about their appointment during the induction period.
- 11.4 Postdoctorates should be provided with adequate working space, equipment and/or regular access to required equipment.
- 11.5 Postdoctorates should be provided with basic administrative facilities, including IT network access, printing, internet use, an institutional email address, library facilities and access to university health services. Postdoctorates should be eligible to apply for parking facilities and membership of sports and other university clubs.

12. Professional development

- 12.1 Training is a central component of the postdoctorate experience. It provides the opportunity for postdoctoral fellows and associates to enhance research skills critical to pursue careers as independent investigators or other related careers. All postdoctoral scholars are thus expected to engage in both training and career development.
- 12.2 Postdoctorates are encouraged to register for skills development workshops and/or short courses available at their host university, provided that sufficient funds exist to sponsor their participation and the enrolment is supported by the relevant host.
- 12.3 Within the first 30 (thirty) days of a postdoctorate's appointment, the postdoctorate and their host must complete an Individual Development Plan (IDP) to define the development expectations of the postdoctorate and host for the duration of the fellowship.

- 12.4 The postdoctorate should provide the host, at least once annually, with a progress report of their research and professional development, as well as goals for the next reporting cycle.
- 12.5 Postdoctorates should be assisted to develop new research initiatives and ideas with the support of relevant structures and initiatives at their host university.

13. Code of Conduct, Grievance and Disciplinary Procedures

Code of Conduct

- 13.1 It is anticipated that each university will have in place codes of conduct for both students and staff. Since postdoctorates are neither students nor staff, each university that hosts postdoctorates should adapt and adopt the most relevant extant code of conduct for the postdoctorates hosted by the university. If the policy makes reference to “the standard” policies, rules, and regulations of the university, and where are different policies and rules pertaining to students and staff, it must be made explicit whether postdoctorates are subject to the policies, rules and regulations of staff or students.
- 13.2 The code of conduct should be appended to, and form part of, the Memorandum of Understanding signed by both the host and postdoctorate.

Grievance procedures

- 13.3 A grievance is any dissatisfaction and/or feeling of injustice in connection with a postdoctorate’s work and/or conditions at the university which is brought to the attention of the relevant authorities.
- 13.4 All universities should include in their policies related to postdoctorates, a clear and detailed process to be followed by postdoctorates and/or their hosts in the case of a grievance arising during the time of a postdoctorate’s award.
- 13.5 Grievances should be resolved at the earliest stage possible and as quickly as possible. The grievance procedure developed by each university must clearly state the allocated maximum amount of time for each step in the procedure. Where it is impracticable to address a grievance within the time limit set out in a university’s grievance procedure, an extension may be agreed upon between the postdoctorate lodging the grievance and the designated representative of the university. Such an extension must be recorded in writing and signed by both parties.
- 13.6 If the postdoctorate who initiates the grievance procedure fails to pursue the complaint through the channels provided for, it must be assumed that she/he abides by the resolution reached by that stage of the procedure or accepts that the complaint has no substance.
- 13.7 A postdoctorate with a grievance may be assisted throughout the procedure by either a representative from the postdoctorate society, postdoctorate office or by any other postdoctorate formally appointed by the university or by a student.
- 13.8 Any decisions made must be recorded in writing and must be accompanied by reasons set out in writing.

Disciplinary procedures

- 13.9 Disciplinary procedures are initiated when there is a claim of misconduct made against a postdoctorate in which such claim is based on a contravention of the university's code of conduct for postdoctorates.
- 13.10 A Disciplinary Committee should be appointed as per the policies and regulations of the university as they pertain to dealing with cases of misconduct.
- 13.11 The Disciplinary Committee shall consist of impartial members who have no prior involvement with the complainant, charged postdoctorate or the situation giving rise to the complaint.

Relationship between the Grievance and Disciplinary Procedures

- 13.12 Grievances are often the result of misunderstanding between two or more parties and misconduct is not necessarily involved. However, where a grievance has been brought to the attention of management and, after investigation, management is satisfied that there is evidence of misconduct on the part of the individual who is the subject of the grievance, the matter must be handled in terms of the Disciplinary Procedure. The postdoctorate who lodged the grievance may be asked to be a witness at a disciplinary enquiry. The decision to invoke the Disciplinary Procedure will normally mark the end of the grievance procedure.
- 13.13 If on application by the grievant or the person grieved against, the relevant Dean or Deputy Vice- Chancellor, as the case may be, is satisfied that the grievance procedure should continue simultaneously or be revived at the conclusion of the disciplinary proceedings, it may be so ordered by the Dean or DVC concerned.

Training

- 13.14 Heads of department, deans and selected staff of postdoctorate offices should be trained on how to manage and facilitate grievance procedures and disciplinary procedures. This is particularly important in the case of postdoctorates because any disciplinary or grievance procedure is likely to receive no support from the university human resource department by virtue of the fact that postdoctorates are not employed by their university.

14. Policy review

- 14.1 Universities should review their postdoctorate policy at least once in every three-year cycle, and/or according to a university's policy on the renewal of institutional policies.
- 14.2 The owner of the postdoctorate policy may review and amend annexures to the policy at any time.
- 14.3 The owner of the postdoctorate policy should consult all relevant stakeholders when making any amendments to the postdoctorate policy.
- 14.4 The postdoctorate office should keep on record any written requests for amendments to be made to the policy.

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